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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in our contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

**EXAMINATION OF THE BASIS FOR THE IMPOSITION OF
HYDROCARBON TAX, ASCERTAINMENT OF CHARGEABLE
PROFITS AND ASSESSMENT IN THE NIGERIAN
PETROLEUM INDUSTRY UNDER THE PETROLEUM
INDUSTRY ACT, 2021**

By

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Ugwemogak U. Fingsi, Esq.²**

Abstract

Before the passage of the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021, taxation in the upstream petroleum sector was regulated by the Petroleum Profits Tax Act, Cap. P13, LFN, 2004, Consequently, what is known as hydrocarbon tax under the regime of the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021 was referred to as the Petroleum Profit Tax under the old regime of the Petroleum Profits Tax Act, repealed by the Petroleum Industry Act, of 2021. Hydrocarbon tax is a major source of revenue to Nigerian government and its contribution to the Nigerian economy cannot be over-emphasized. The Nigerian Petroleum industry is divided into three parts; the upstream sector; the downstream section and the midstream sector. Before 1958, taxation in the three sectors was regulated by the Companies Income Tax Acts and its impact on Nigeria's economy was not much when compared to the situation where oil is the base of the Nigerian economy. Therefore, the objective of this research is to engage in painstaking appraisal and analysis of the provisions of the PIA, relating to hydrocarbon taxation in Nigeria with a view to unearthing what constitutes impediments to the proper and accurate ascertainment of the crude oil revenue of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations as well as accurate hydrocarbon assessment and taxation. Thus, this work examines the basis for the imposition of hydrocarbon tax on the profits of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations and how the profits chargeable to tax such as adjusted profit, assessable profits, and chargeable profits are ascertained. It also examines certain allowable and unallowable deductions. The

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paper examined the concept of assessable and chargeable tax as well as the assessment of the profits of the companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations having regard to the basic type of assessment contemplated by the Petroleum Industry Act, of 2021. This is carefully done to aid the accurate taxation of hydrocarbon tax since tax liability is not imposed on the entire profits of the company. This research answers research problems such as; what constitute hydrocarbon under the Act? what is the determinant of the profits of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations in view of the fact that the scope of what constitute hydrocarbon is not delineated in the Act? It adopts the doctrinal research methodology which is the research into law as it is. Thus, this research is based on the study of the principal statute which is, the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021, as well as other literatures such as text books and articles. The research finds that, the Act sets out to impose hydrocarbon tax on the profit of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations, however, the Act does not define what constitutes hydrocarbon and it is recommended that, the provisions of the Act should be amended in order to provide a clear definition of the word “hydrocarbon” and delineate the scope of what constitute hydrocarbon for the purpose of certainty and fairness of hydrocarbon tax regime.

Keywords: *Assessment, Chargeable tax, Hydrocarbon tax, Upstream Petroleum Operations.*

1.0 Introduction

The responsibility for the administration of hydrocarbon tax was previously vested on the Federal Inland Revenue Services. However, with the passage of the Nigeria Revenue Service (Establishment) 2025³ following the tax reform of the President Tinubu administration, the administration of hydrocarbon tax is now vested in the Nigeria Revenue Service.⁴ Prior to the passing of the Petroleum Industry Act, (PIA)⁵ taxation in the upstream petroleum industry was governed by the Petroleum Profits Tax Act⁶. The Petroleum Industry Act,⁷ imposes tax on the profits of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations in Nigeria. However, the determinant of the amount payable by a company involves the assessment of the company's profits and ascertaining the tax payable by such a company in the accounting period in reference. It is therefore insufficient for the tax to be imposed on the profits of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations without proper ascertainment and assessment of the tax payable. Thus, profits chargeable to tax must be correctly ascertained and assessed taking into account the statutorily permitted guidelines for proper taxation of profits of that company.

The PIA, sets out to impose tax called hydrocarbon tax on the profits of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations but failed to define hydrocarbon, therefore, for a seamless tax regime under the Act it is imperative that the following problems be resolved effectively;

1. What constitute hydrocarbon under the Act?
2. What is the determinant of the profits of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations in view of the fact that the scope of what constitute hydrocarbon is not delineated in the Act?
3. How is the crude oil revenue of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations ascertained for the purpose of hydrocarbon tax without knowing the scope of what constitute hydrocarbon under the Act?

3. The Nigeria Revenue Service (Establishment) Act, 2025 repealed the Federal Inland Revenue Service (Establishment) Act, 2007.

4. Section 3 of the Nigeria Revenue Service (Establishment) Act. 2025.

5. PIA, 2021.

6. Cap. 13 LFN, 2004

7. s. 261 PIA, 2021

Significantly, resolving the above research problems is key to the accurate assessment and collection of hydrocarbon tax since the accurate assessment of the profits taxable under the Act and the delineation of what constitute hydrocarbon form the key to an equitable and transparent fiscal regime in the upstream petroleum sector. The aim of this research is to engage in painstaking appraisal and analysis of the provisions of the Petroleum Industry Act, relating to hydrocarbon taxation in Nigeria with a view to unearthing what constitutes impediments to the proper and accurate ascertainment of the crude oil revenue of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations as well as accurate hydrocarbon assessment and taxation while the objectives of this research are:

1. To examine the provisions of the PIA, as it affects hydrocarbon taxation.
2. To determine the type of companies that are engaged in upstream petroleum operations and thus subjected to hydrocarbon taxation under the PIA.
3. To consider the issue of ascertainment of profits, chargeable profits, adjusted profit and assessable profits of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations.

This research adopts the doctrinal research method which is the research into law as it is. Thus, this research is based on the study of the relevant statutes such as, the Petroleum Industry Act,⁸ the Petroleum Profits Tax Act,⁹ as well as case laws and legal materials such as, Text Books, Journals and Articles, among others. It is the findings of this research that, hydrocarbon taxation is a major source of government revenue in Nigeria and to enhance the effective administration of hydrocarbon tax in the upstream petroleum sector, there is therefore need for a special attention to be given to the administration, collection and assessment of hydrocarbon tax. Also, the Act sets out to impose hydrocarbon tax on the profit of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations, however, the Act does not define what constitutes hydrocarbon, or delineates the scope of what constitute hydrocarbon tax. It is therefore, recommended that the PIA should be amended to make provision for a clear definition and or delineation of what constitute hydrocarbon tax.

2.0 Basis for the imposition of Hydrocarbon Tax

⁸. PIA, 2021

⁹. Cap. P13 LFN, 2004.

According to Oke,¹⁰ “petroleum profit tax, is imposed on the profit derived from petroleum operations.” Petroleum profit tax is what is today known as hydrocarbon tax under the present regime of the Petroleum Industry Act,¹¹ though, the scope of the application of hydrocarbon tax has been widened to apply to crude oil as well as field condensates and liquid natural gas derived from associated gas and produced in the field upstream of the measurement point.¹² The imposition of hydrocarbon tax is targeted at the profit of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations, thus, engagement in upstream petroleum operations forms the basis for the imposition of hydrocarbon tax.¹³

The payment of hydrocarbon tax on the profits of any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations is a debt obligation payable by the company. This was the position of the Supreme Court in *Shell Petroleum Development Company Nigeria Limited v. F.B.I.R*¹⁴ where it held thus¹⁵:

Since by the provisions of section 41 (1) of the Petroleum Profits Tax Act, the Federal Board of Inland Revenue may sue for and recover tax in a court of competent jurisdiction, as a debt due to the Government of the Federation, thus the obligation to pay petroleum profits tax is the same as the obligation to pay the debt. The payment of a debt by a going concern or company is incidental to the operations of such an organization.¹⁶

¹⁰. Yemi Oke, *Nigerian Energy Resources Law and Practice, Oil and Gas Law (Practice, Cases and Theories)*, (Princeton and Associates Publishing Co. Ltd, 2019), 222

¹¹. PIA, 2021.

¹². s 260 PIA, 2021

¹³. Section 261 PIA, 2021

¹⁴. (1996) 8 NWLR (PT. 466) 256 @ 285-286

¹⁵. Ibid @ pages 285-286

¹⁶. Ibid.

Lawal,¹⁷ posits that “the legal basis for imposition and payment of petroleum profit tax by companies engaged in petroleum operations in Nigeria is contained in Section 8 of the Petroleum Profits Tax Act,¹⁸.” This implies that under the Petroleum Profits Tax Act,¹⁹ Section 8 was the statutory foundation upon which petroleum profits tax was levied on the profits of any company engaged in petroleum operations. However, under the current regime of the Petroleum Industry Act,²⁰ the statutory basis for the imposition of hydrocarbon tax on the profits of any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations is now Section 261 of the Act.²¹ What constitutes the phrase “upstream petroleum operations” has been defined to mean the exploration for, appraisal of, development of and winning or obtaining of petroleum in Nigeria by or on behalf of a company on its own account for commercial purposes.²² As stated earlier, the provisions of Section 261 of the Act,²³ forms the statutory foundation for the imposition of hydrocarbon tax under the present legal regime. The said section²⁴ provides as follows:

There shall be levied upon the profits of any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations in relation to crude oil a tax to be known as hydrocarbon tax, which shall be charged and assessed upon its profits related to the operations and payable during each accounting period by the provisions of this Act.

The above provision of the Act²⁵ reveals three (3) essential ingredients that require clarification in the imposition of hydrocarbon tax. These three essential ingredients are: (a) The Profit; (b) The Accounting period and (c) Upstream Petroleum operations.

¹⁷. Lawal K.T, Taxation of Petroleum Profit Under the Nigeria’s Petroleum Profits Tax Act, *International Journal of Advance Legal Studies and Governance*, Vol. 4 No. 2, August, 2013, available at <https://www.academia.edu/>. Accessed on 18th July, 2025.

¹⁸. Cap. P 13 LFN, 2004

¹⁹. Ibid.

²⁰. PIA, 2021

²¹. Ibid.

²². Section 318 PIA, 2021

²³. PIA, 2021

²⁴. Section 261 *ibid.*

²⁵. *Ibid.*

The three ingredients are therefore clarified as follows:

a. The Profits

The Act²⁶, does not define the term “profit” however, Section 2 of the Petroleum Profits Tax Act²⁷ defines the profits of a company as the aggregate of;

- i. The proceeds of the sale of all chargeable oil sold by a company in the period in focus.
- ii. The value of all chargeable oil disposed of by the company in the period in focus.
- iii. All income of the company of the period in focus incidental to and arising from any one or more of the company’s operations.

Significantly, what constitutes the value of any chargeable oil disposed of by a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations is regarded as the aggregate of the value of that crude oil determined for royalties for all fields by the Petroleum Industry Act or any applicable law.²⁸ Therefore, to determine the profits of any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations it is important that the total aggregate of the proceeds of the sale of all chargeable oil, the value of all chargeable oil disposed of by the company, and all the income of the company incidental to and arising from the company’s upstream petroleum operations be taken into account.²⁹

b. Accounting period

The accounting period for imposition of hydrocarbon tax is a period of one year commencing on 1st January and terminating on the 31st December of that same year³⁰ or any shorter period starting from the day the company makes its first sale or bulk disposal of chargeable oil, domestic, export or both, and ending on the 31st December of that same year. The accounting period of a company could be any period of less than a year where such a company ceases at any time of the year to be engaged in upstream petroleum operations.³¹ In other words, the accounting period could be any period of

²⁶. PIA

²⁷. Now repealed by Section 310 (1) (g) PIA, 2021.

²⁸. Section 262 (2) PIA.

²⁹. Section 262 PIA, 2021 and Section 9 (2) of the PPTA.

³⁰Section 318 (b) PIA.

³¹. Section 318 (c) PIA.

less than a year commencing on 1st January and ending on the date the company ceases to be engaged in upstream petroleum operations in that same year.³²

However, in the event of a dispute in respect to the date which a company makes its first sale or disposal of chargeable oil or the date which that company ceases to be engaged in petroleum operations such dispute shall be determined by the Commission³³ and no appeal shall lie against the decision.³⁴ The denial of the right of appeal to any company aggrieved by the decision of the Commission appears to emphasize the point that the law is not interested in the day a company makes its first sale or dispose of chargeable oil in the year or the particular date which a company ceases to be engaged in petroleum operations as far as such event takes place within the year.

The focus, therefore, lies in the accounting period of the company commenced from any of such time irrespective of the particular date and ending on the 31st of December of that same year. Ayua³⁵ opined that the liability of a company that is engaged in petroleum operations to pay petroleum profits tax is based on the accounting period of the company and not by reference to the year of the assessment of that company.³⁶ On the other hand, what is important for the assessment of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations for payment of hydrocarbon tax is the accounting period of that company. The implication is that a company that engages in upstream petroleum operations is obliged to pay its tax liability in the accounting period under review. More so, as hydrocarbon tax is only charged and assessed on the profits of any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations and payable during the particular accounting period in reference.³⁷

c. Upstream Petroleum operations

³². Ibid.

³³. Section 318 *ibid.* Note that the Commission means the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission

³⁴. Ibid.

³⁵. Ayua I. A, *The Nigerian Tax Law*, (Spectrum Law Publishing, 1996), 194

³⁶. Ibid.

³⁷. s. 261 PIA 2021

The Act³⁸ did not give a concise definition of upstream petroleum operations but enumerated the category of activities that constitute upstream petroleum operations and this makes the definition ambiguous. This is in contrast to the Petroleum Profits Tax Act,³⁹ which defines a company engaged in petroleum operations as one involved in the winning or obtaining of petroleum by mining or drilling,⁴⁰ this has widened the scope of engagement in upstream petroleum operations.⁴¹ Though the definition of upstream petroleum operations by the Act appears ambiguous, the point is, when a company's activities fall under any of the categories of activities mentioned in the above provision then such a company is said to be engaged in upstream petroleum operations for hydrocarbon tax. Therefore, engagement in upstream petroleum operations is the basis for the imposition of hydrocarbon tax under the Act and this has to be arrived at by examining the categories of activities envisaged by the Act.

3.0 Ascertainment of Profits

The accurate collection and payment of hydrocarbon tax commences with the proper ascertainment of the profits of a company. This is crucial to the proper collection and payment of hydrocarbon tax. According to Etikerentse⁴² the company's profits ascertainable under the Petroleum Profits Tax Act for purposes of taxation must be related to the company's incomes in a given accounting period.⁴³ Thus, the ascertainment of the profits of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations is the first important step for a proper collection of hydrocarbon tax.

The applied principle in determining the actual taxable profits of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations is the same with other companies not engaged in

³⁸. Section 318, PIA.

³⁹. Section 2, repealed PPTA

⁴⁰ According to Section 2 of the PPTA; petroleum operations means the winning or obtaining and transportation of petroleum or chargeable oil in Nigeria by or on behalf of a company for its own account by any drilling, mining, extracting or other like operations or process, not including the company refining at a refinery, in the course of a business carried on by the company engaged in such operations, and all operations incidental thereto and any sale of or any disposal of chargeable oil by or on behalf of the company.

⁴¹. Section 318 PIA is to the effect that upstream Petroleum operations means the exploration for appraisal of, development of and winning or obtaining of petroleum in Nigeria by or on behalf of a company on its own account for commercial purposes, petroleum exploration operations, the drilling of exploration, appraisal and development wells, all activities upstream of the measurement points, related to the winning of petroleum...

⁴². Etikerentse G, *Nigerian Petroleum Law*, (2nd Edition, Dredew Publishers, 2004), 251

⁴³. *Ibid.*

upstream petroleum operations,⁴⁴ that is to say, certain items in the company's expenditure are by law permitted to be deducted from the gross profits of the company and the criteria for identifying the expenses which qualify for the deduction is to determine whether such expenses were wholly and exclusively incurred during that accounting period.⁴⁵ Such deductible expenses must be necessary for the upstream petroleum operations of the company, That is, the expenses must be incurred in the course of generating the taxable income of the company and it is immaterial whether the expenditure is incurred within or outside Nigeria.⁴⁶ Therefore, to arrive at the appropriate amount of the taxable profits of any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations the following must be considered⁴⁷ namely, i. The adjusted profits, ii. The assessable profits, and iii. The chargeable profits. The determination of the above three important concepts is key to a proper assessment of the profit of the company chargeable to tax under the Act ⁴⁸ useful in giving an accurate understanding of the actual profits chargeable to tax under the Act.⁴⁹

3.1 Adjusted Profit

The adjusted profit of a company is the balance of the profits earned by that company in an accounting period after the deduction of certain expenses and outgoings.⁵⁰ According to the Act⁵¹ adjusted profits of an accounting period shall be the profits of that period after the deductions of expenses wholly, reasonably, exclusively, and necessarily incurred during that period.⁵² In computing, the adjusted profit of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations in an accounting period the law allows for the deduction of expenses wholly, exclusively, and necessarily incurred by that company during the accounting period.⁵³ The question is what expenses are wholly, exclusively, and necessarily incurred by a company engaged in upstream

⁴⁴. Ibid p. 252

⁴⁵. Ibid.

⁴⁶. Section 10 (1) PPTA, repealed by the PIA, 2021.

⁴⁷. Ayua I. A, *The Nigerian Tax Law*, already cited, 195

⁴⁸. The PIA, 2021.

⁴⁹. Ibid

⁵⁰. Etikerentse G, 253

⁵¹. Section 262 (3) and 263 (1) of the PIA.

⁵²Ibid

⁵³. Section 263 (1) PIA.

petroleum operations? The Act does not specifically define what the phrase “expenses wholly, exclusively, and necessarily incurred during that period” means. However, the Supreme Court in the case of *Shell Petroleum Development Company Nigeria Limited v. F.B.I.R*⁵⁴ held per Uwais C.J.N thus:

According to the ordinary dictionary meaning the words ‘wholly’ and ‘exclusively’ have virtually the same meaning. They can be said to mean ‘solely’ or ‘entirely’. The dictionary meaning of the word ‘necessarily’ is the same as that of the words ‘inevitably’ and ‘unquestionably’. Therefore, was the payment of the Bank Charges solely and inevitably incurred for the petroleum operations of the appellant? As already seen the payment of the Central Bank Charges was imposed on the appellant by the Federal Government vide Exhibit 5. The appellant is expected to receive directives from the Federal Government from time to time in the course of its business which is ‘petroleum operations’. This is incidental to such operations. I have no doubt whatsoever in my mind about that. The payment of bank charges to the Central Bank of Nigeria which had not rendered any service to the appellant but simply because the Federal Government had so directed was inevitable and was, therefore, incurred in the course of the appellant’s business which was petroleum operations.

The Court further held⁵⁵ that “Once there is a statutory or contractual obligation (in this case it is statutory) for a company engaged in petroleum operations to perform, such obligation is ‘wholly, exclusively and necessarily for the operations of the company’”. As such the expenses incurred ought to qualify as necessarily incurred for petroleum operations. Therefore, the phrase “expenses wholly, exclusively and

⁵⁴. *Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria Ltd. v. Federal Board of Inland Revenue* (1996) 8 NWLR (Part 466) 255 case at pages 290-291

⁵⁵. *Ibid* at p. 295.

necessarily incurred” is defined to mean expenses solely or entirely and inevitably or unquestionably incurred for petroleum operations of any company.⁵⁶ Consequently, unless expenses are deemed to be wholly, exclusively, and necessarily incurred they will not qualify for deduction under the provision of Section 263 (1) of the Act.⁵⁷

3.2 Assessable profits

The Act⁵⁸ provides that; “the assessable profits for each company or petroleum mining lease for any accounting period shall be the amount of the adjusted profit of that period after the deduction of the amount of any loss incurred by that company during any previous accounting period”.

According to Oke,⁵⁹ assessable profits are defined to mean the adjusted profit with fewer deductions allowed under section 16. Similarly, Lawal⁶⁰ defines assessable profit thus; “This refers to adjusted profit less the loss incurred by the company during the previous accounting year by section 16”. It is contended here that to refer to assessable profit as “adjusted profit less the loss incurred by the company during the previous accounting year with section 16” is quite misleading and blurs the understanding of what assessable profit means. The correct approach to understanding what assessable profit means would be a combined reading of the provisions of Sections 318 and 262 of the Act.⁶¹

3.3 Chargeable profits

The Act⁶² provides that “chargeable profits of any company for any accounting period shall be the amount of the assessable profits of that period after the deduction of any amount to be allowed with the provisions of this section”. According to Oke,⁶³ chargeable profit is the amount of assessable profit of the accounting period minus

⁵⁶. Shell Petroleum Dev. Company Nigeria Ltd. V. F.B.I.R. Cited already.

⁵⁷. PIA, 2021.

⁵⁸. Section 265 (1) PIA

⁵⁹. Yemi Oke, *Nigerian Energy Resources Law and Practice*, (2019) cited already. 229.

⁶⁰. Lawal K. T, *Taxation of Petroleum Profit under the Nigeria’s Petroleum Profit Tax Act*. Cited already 11.

⁶¹. PIA, 2021.

⁶². Section 266 (1) PIA.

⁶³. Yemi Oke, *Nigerian Energy Resources Law and Practice*, cited already.

capital allowances as provided in the second schedule to the Act.⁶⁴ It is also defined as the amount of assessable profit of the accounting period less the total of capital allowances provided in the second schedule to the Act.⁶⁵ Succinctly, Chargeable profit is the amount of assessable profit after the deduction of any amount allowed as a capital allowance.⁶⁶

The law allows for the grant of capital allowance to any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations instead of depreciation⁶⁷ and such allowances include, the acquisition of right over petroleum deposits, the construction of buildings that are of no value after the petroleum operations, searching for and discovery and testing of petroleum deposits and winning therein.⁶⁸ However, under the new legal regime⁶⁹ the deduction of any amount to be allowed under Section 266 of the Act,⁷⁰ is:

- i. The aggregate amount of capital allowances due to the company under the Fifth Schedule.⁷¹
- ii. The aggregate amount of all production allowances due to the company under the provisions of the Six Schedule.⁷²
- iii. In the case of acquisition costs of petroleum rights, the value of the right and the value of the assets acquired shall be reported separately.⁷³

4.0 Deductions

It is noteworthy, that by the nature of petroleum operations, certain expenses are bound to be necessarily incurred by a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations either preliminary to the exploration activities or after it. There are some instances where such expenses could be tied to the income produced directly or would

⁶⁴. Ibid at 230

⁶⁵. Lawal K. T, *Taxation of Petroleum Profit under the Nigeria's Petroleum Profit Tax Act*, (2013) cited already, 12

⁶⁶. Ibid.

⁶⁷. Yemi Oke, *Nigerian Energy Resources Law and Practice*, (2019), 230

⁶⁸. Ibid.

⁶⁹. PIA, 2021.

⁷⁰. Ibid.

⁷¹. Section 266 (a) Ibid.

⁷². Section 266 (b) Ibid.

⁷³. Section 266 (c) Ibid.

have been incurred for the petroleum operations but have not produced income or profits.⁷⁴ Whatever the case; the law contemplates such a situation and allows for certain deductions from the profits of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations before being charged to tax under the Act⁷⁵. There are however ,certain deductions not allowed by the Act.⁷⁶ Thus the deductions allowed by law are known as allowable deductions while the deductions not allowed are known as disallowable deductions.

The emphasis is that due to the heavy financial burden that companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations arising the high cost of investment, tax regime, and the volatile nature of the oil-producing areas, certain tax allowances, and incentives are granted under the Act to cushion these effect.⁷⁷ These tax allowances and incentives are outlined below:

- i. Allowable deductions
- ii. Capital allowance and
- iii. Petroleum investment tax allowance or tax credit allowance⁷⁸

These allowances and incentives are known as allowable deductions. Therefore, the deductions allowed and those deductions disallowed are herein considered *viz*:

4.1 Allowable deduction

The Act⁷⁹ allows any company which is engaged in upstream petroleum operations to make certain deductions before the profit payable as hydrocarbon tax is calculated.⁸⁰ Therefore, in computing the adjusted profit of a company in upstream petroleum

⁷⁴. Lawal K. T, *Taxation of Petroleum Profit under the Nigeria's Petroleum Profit Tax Act*, cited already. 9

⁷⁵. PIA

⁷⁶. Section 264 Ibid.

⁷⁷. Asada D. & Olong M. A, *Appraising Taxation and the Nigerian Oil Industry*. In Agbonika J. A. A (Ed.) *Topical Issues on Nigerian Tax Laws and Related Areas*. Ababa Press Ltd, (2015), 181.

⁷⁸. Ibid.

⁷⁹. Section 263(1) PIA.

⁸⁰. Lawal K. T, *Taxation of Petroleum Profit under the Nigeria's Petroleum Profit Tax Act*, cited already. 9

operations, such a company is entitled to deduct expenses wholly, exclusively, and necessarily incurred during that period.⁸¹

Under the old regime,⁸² the position was that where a deduction is not possible under the provision of section 10 (1) of the Act⁸³ then such can be accommodated under any of the paragraphs to the section.⁸⁴ Thus the Supreme Court held per Ogundare J.S.C⁸⁵ that the provision of section 10 (1) of the Act is wide enough to encompass the exchange losses and that the fact that it does not come within any of the items (a)-(g) specifically provided for in the subsection 10 does not take it out of the wide embrace of the subsection. Therefore, whenever deduction was not possible under paragraph (a)-(g) of S. 10 of the Act then such deduction might fall under the provision of S. 10 (1) of the Act, allows outgoings and expenses sought to be deducted as wholly, exclusively and necessarily incurred for petroleum operations during an accounting period. However, under the new regime,⁸⁶ the Act⁸⁷ sets out items that qualify as expenses wholly, reasonably, exclusively, and necessarily incurred during an accounting period. Nevertheless, the items set out are not intended to be exhaustive.

4.2 Deduction not allowed

The emphasis is that in as much as the Act makes provisions for certain deductions to be made from the profit of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations, there are also categories of deduction that the Act does not permit ascertaining the adjusted profit of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations.⁸⁸ It appears that the essence of expressly disallowing certain deductions by the Act is to guide against instances where companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations will be

⁸¹. Section 263 (1) PIA.

⁸². PPTA repealed.

⁸³. Section 10 (1) *ibid*.

⁸⁴. Paragraph a-I *ibid*.

⁸⁵. In *Shell Pet. Dev. Co. (Nig.) Ltd. v. F. B. I.R* (1996) cited already. 304-305.

⁸⁶. PIA

⁸⁷. Section 263 (1) *Ibid*.

⁸⁸. Section 264 PIA.

shielded by the Act to avoid the responsibility to pay tax. From the provisions of the Act,⁸⁹ the following deductions are not allowed⁹⁰, viz:

- a. Disbursement or expenses not being money wholly, reasonably, exclusive, and necessarily incurred for those operations.⁹¹
- b. Expenditure for the purchase of information relating to the existence and extent of petroleum deposits, other than for the acquisition of geophysical, geological, and geochemical data and information.⁹²
- c. Expenditure incurred as a penalty, natural gas flare fees, or imposition relating to natural gas flare.⁹³
- d. Financial or bank charges, arbitration and litigation costs, bad debts, and interest on borrowing.⁹⁴
- e. Head office or affiliate costs shared costs, research and development costs, or any other shared indirect production costs.⁹⁵
- f. Production bonuses, signature bonuses paid for the acquisition of or of rights in or over petroleum deposits, bonuses or fees paid for renewing petroleum mining lease or petroleum prospecting license or marginal field, or fees paid for assigning rights to another party.⁹⁶
- g. Tax inputted into a contract or an agreement on a net tax basis and paid by a company on behalf of the vendor or contractor.⁹⁷
- h. Capital withdrawn or sum employed or intended to be employed as capital.⁹⁸
- i. Capital employed in improvements as distinct from repairs.⁹⁹

⁸⁹. Ibid

⁹⁰. Ibid.

⁹¹. Section 264 (a) Ibid.

⁹². Section 264 (b) PIA.

⁹³. Section 264 (c) Ibid.

⁹⁴. Section 264 (d) Ibid.

⁹⁵. Section 264 (e) Ibid.

⁹⁶. Section 264 (f) PIA.

⁹⁷. Section 264 (g) Ibid.

⁹⁸. Section 264 (h) Ibid.

⁹⁹. Section 264 (i) Ibid.

- j. Sum recoverable under an insurance or contract of indemnity, except an amount that is not recovered under the scheme.¹⁰⁰
- k. Rent of or cost of repairs to any premises or part of premises not incurred for those operations.¹⁰¹
- l. Amounts incurred in respect of tertiary education tax, company income tax, any income tax, profits tax, or other similar taxes, whether charged within Nigeria or elsewhere.¹⁰²
- m. The depreciation of any premises, building, structures, works of a permanent nature, plant, machinery, or fixtures.¹⁰³
- n. Payment to provident, savings widows and orphans, or other society, scheme, or fund.¹⁰⁴
- o. Contribution to a pension, provident or other society scheme or fund for production staff approved by the National Pension Commission.¹⁰⁵
- p. All customs duties.¹⁰⁶
- q. Costs under paragraph 2 (2) (c) of the Sixth Schedule.¹⁰⁷

The point is that under allowable deductions certain deductions might be allowed if they fall into the purview of the expression “expenses wholly, exclusively, and necessarily incurred during that period”. However, deductions not allowed are specifically set out by the Act.¹⁰⁸ Thus, expenses that fall into the categories of the expenses explicitly set out will automatically constitute deductions not allowed.

5.0 Chargeable Profits and Chargeable Tax

¹⁰⁰. Section 264 (j) Ibid.

¹⁰¹. Section 264 (k) Ibid.

¹⁰². Section 264 (l) Ibid.

¹⁰³. Section 264 (m) Ibid.

¹⁰⁴. Section 264 (n) Ibid.

¹⁰⁵. Section 264 (o) Ibid.

¹⁰⁶. Section 264 (p) Ibid.

¹⁰⁷. Section 264 (q) PIA. The provision of Paragraph 2 (2) (c) of the Sixth Schedule to the Act, provides that “where under paragraph 2 (2) (b) any cost exceed the cost price ratio limit upon the termination of upstream petroleum operations related to crude oil, such costs shall not be deductible for purpose of calculation of the hydrocarbon tax”.

¹⁰⁸. Section 264 Ibid.

The chargeable profits of any company for an accounting period is the amount of the assessable profits of that period after the deduction of the following amounts:¹⁰⁹

- a. The aggregate amount of capital allowances due to the company under the provisions of the Fifth Schedule.¹¹⁰
- b. The aggregate amount of all production allowances due to the company provisions of the Sixth Schedule.¹¹¹
- c. Costs of petroleum rights, the value of rights, and the value of the assets acquired shall be eligible for an annual allowance of 20% per annum.¹¹²

The assessable tax refers to tax arrived at using the appropriate tax rate on the chargeable profit.¹¹³ According to Oke,¹¹⁴ the tax rate is applied to the chargeable profit to get assessable tax as follows; (i) for the first five accounting periods of a new company the rate is 65.75%, and (ii) for another accounting period the rate is 85%.¹¹⁵

On the other hand, chargeable tax is the final amount in the computation process for petroleum profits for the accounting period.¹¹⁶ Chargeable tax for any accounting period of a company is the percentage of the chargeable profit for that period aggregate which shall be 30% of the profit from crude oil for petroleum mining leases in respect of onshore and shallow water areas and 15% of the profit from crude oil for onshore and shallow water for petroleum prospecting licenses.¹¹⁷ However, where for any accounting period of a company, the amount of the chargeable tax for that period is less than the amount the company is liable to pay an additional amount of chargeable tax and the whole of any additional chargeable tax for crude oil and associated gas

¹⁰⁹. Section 266 (1) Ibid.

¹¹⁰. Section 266 (1) (a) PIA.

¹¹¹. Section 266 (1) (b) Ibid.

¹¹². Section 266 (1) (c) Ibid.

¹¹³. K. T. Lawal (2013) *Taxation of Petroleum Profit under the Nigeria's Petroleum Profit Tax Act*, cited already, 13.

¹¹⁴. Yemi Oke, *Nigerian Energy Resources Law and Practice*, (2019) cited already, 233

¹¹⁵. Yemi Oke, *Nigerian Energy Resources Law and Practice*, cited already. 233

¹¹⁶. Kalu, V. E. *Nigeria's Petroleum Profits Tax Act: An Assessment*, available on www.nigerianlawguru.com. Accessed on 15th October, 2018.

¹¹⁷. Section 267 (a) and (b) PIA. .

payable shall be concurrently paid with the final instalment of the chargeable tax payable for that period.¹¹⁸

6.0 Tax Assessments

The power to raise an assessment on any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations in any accounting period, for the payment of hydrocarbon tax is vested in the Service;¹¹⁹ however, this power is only exercisable where a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations, failed to deliver self-assessment within the period provided,¹²⁰ or such extension of time as the Service may grant in writing where a good reason has been shown to the satisfaction of the service.¹²¹ The law¹²² requires every company engaged in upstream petroleum operations, for each accounting period, to make up accounts of its profits or losses and prepare certain particulars to determine hydrocarbon tax, among which are:¹²³

- a. A statement of accounts of its losses.
- b. Computations of its actual adjusted profit or loss and actual assessable profits of that period.
- c. A schedule showing:
 - i. The residues at the end of that period in respect of its assets
 - ii. All qualifying petroleum expenditure incurred by it in that period
 - iii. The values of any of its assets disposed of in that period.
 - iv. The allowances due to it under that schedule for that period.
- d. A schedule showing total production allowance from every field of its upstream petroleum operations related to crude oil.
- e. A computation of its actual chargeable profits for that period for the two classes of chargeable profits.¹²⁴

¹¹⁸. Section 268 (1) and (4) Ibid.

¹¹⁹. Section 282 (1) *ibid*.

¹²⁰. *Ibid*.

¹²¹. Section 281 (1) PIA.

¹²². Section 277 (1) *Ibid*.

¹²³. Section 277 (i) *Ibid*

¹²⁴. The two classes of chargeable profits identified in Section 267 (a) and (b) are as follows: (a) 30% of the profit from crude oil for petroleum mining leases selected under Section 93 (6) (b) and (7) (b) of this Act with respect to onshore and shallow water areas; and (b) 15% of profit from crude oil for onshore and shallow water and for petroleum prospecting licences selected under Section 93 (6) (a) and (7) (a) of this Act.

- f. A statement of amounts repaid, refunded, waived, or released to it during that period.¹²⁵
- g. A computation of its chargeable tax for that period.¹²⁶
- h. Duly completed self-assessment form attested to by the principal officer of the company.
- i. Evidence of payment of the final instalment.¹²⁷

The Act¹²⁸ requires that every company which engages in upstream petroleum operations, in every accounting period of that company and within five months after the expiration of that period or five months after the effective date of the Act, deliver to the Service a copy of its accounts which bears an auditors certificate and copies of the particulars mentioned above. Where the copies are not estimates they must contain a declaration signed by an authorized officer of the company that same is true and complete.¹²⁹ However, where the copies are estimates then they must contain a declaration signed by an officer of the company that the estimate was made to the best of the ability of the person signing it.¹³⁰ But where a company is yet to commence bulk sales or disposal of chargeable oil, then that company shall file with the Service its audited accounts and returns.¹³¹

The Service has the power to give notice in writing to any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations requiring the company to furnish it, within a reasonable time as it may determine fuller or further information of that company's accounts or other matters considered necessary for the Act.¹³² Also, to enable the

¹²⁵. Referred to in Section 263 which are in respect of allowable deductions.

¹²⁶. Where associated gas is being sold or otherwise delivered through the measurement point the methodology used to determine the chargeable tax.

¹²⁷. Section 277 (1) a-I, PIA.

¹²⁸. Section 277 (2) Ibid

¹²⁹. However, where the company is in liquidation, the declaration must be signed by the company liquidator, receiver or the agent of the liquidator or receiver. Section 277 (2) (a) Petroleum Industry Act, Op. cit.

¹³⁰. Section 277 (2) (b) Ibid.

¹³¹. Section 3 PIA. Note that the audited accounts and returns shall be filed within 18 months from the date of incorporation, in the case of a newly incorporated company or within 5 months after any period ending on 31st December, in the case of any other company, provided that where there is an interval between 31st December of the preceding year and the date on which the company commences the bulk sale or disposal of chargeable oil, the interval shall be deemed to form part of the preceding period.

¹³². Section 278 PIA.

Service to obtain full information on the upstream petroleum operations of any company the Act empowers the Service to give notice requiring that company within, 21 days from the date of service of such notice, complete and deliver to the service such information requested for in that notice and additionally or in the alternative require an authorized representative of that company to attend and produce for examination any books, documents, accounts, and particulars which the service considers necessary.¹³³ Not later than two months after the commencement of each accounting period of any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations, that company shall submit to the Service an estimated return of its profits or losses for that accounting period for payment of hydrocarbon tax.¹³⁴ Where a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations is unable to prepare and deliver its accounts and particulars to the service within the stipulated time or comply with any notice given to it in line with the Act,¹³⁵ if a good reason is shown to the satisfaction of the service, an extension of time may be granted in writing, as the service may deem necessary.¹³⁶ However, after the expiration of the time allowed for any company engaged in upstream petroleum operations to deliver its accounts and particulars to the service, the act allows the Service to proceed to assess that company with the hydrocarbon tax for that accounting period.¹³⁷ But, where a company has delivered a self-assessment for any accounting period as required, the Service may;¹³⁸

(a) Accept the self-assessment; or

(b) Refuse to accept the self-assessment and proceed to estimate the amount of the tax to be paid by that company for that accounting period and make an assessment.¹³⁹

The assessment of hydrocarbon tax is to be made in the form or manner as the Service shall authorize and must contain the names and addresses of the companies assessed to tax or of the person in whose name the company is assessed to tax, as well as the

¹³³. Ibid.

¹³⁴. Section 280 (1) Ibid.

¹³⁵. Section 281 (1) Ibid

¹³⁶. Section 281 (1) Ibid.

¹³⁷. Section 282 (1) ibid.

¹³⁸. Section 282 (2) and (3) Ibid

¹³⁹. Ibid.

particular accounting period and the amount of the chargeable profits and chargeable tax for that period.¹⁴⁰ Once a company is assessed to hydrocarbon tax, the Service shall cause to be served on that company, either personally or sent by a courier, a notice of assessment stating¹⁴¹:

- (i) The accounting period and the amount of its chargeable profits and chargeable tax assessed and charged upon the company.¹⁴²
- (ii) The place where payment of the tax should be made.¹⁴³
- (iii) Rights of the company to apply to the Service to review and revise the assessment.¹⁴⁴

When a company disputes an assessment made by the Service, it has a right to apply to the Service, within 30 days¹⁴⁵ from the date of the service of the notice, by notice of objection in writing to review and revise the assessment.¹⁴⁶ Such application must state the amount of chargeable profits of the company for the accounting period in which the assessment is made and the tax which it is claimed should be stated on the notice of assessment.¹⁴⁷ No assessment made by the provisions of the Act shall be quashed, voidable, or null and void for want of form or because of mistake, defect, or omission provided that such assessment is in substance and effect in conformity with the intent of the Act and the company assessed or intended to be assessed is designated according to common intent and understanding.¹⁴⁸ Basically, under the Act,¹⁴⁹ the existing types of assessment are; (a)Original assessment (b)Estimated assessment (C)Additional assessment (c)Amended assessment (d)Revised assessment €Final and conclusive

¹⁴⁰. Section 284 (1) Ibid.

¹⁴¹. Section 285 (1) *ibid*.

¹⁴². Section 285 (1) (a) *Ibid*.

¹⁴³. Section 285 (1) (b) *Ibid*.

¹⁴⁴. Section 285 (1) (c) and Subsection 2, PIA.

¹⁴⁵. The Service may extend the period of 30 days upon being satisfied that due to absence from Nigeria, sickness or other reasonable cause, the person in whose name the assessment was made was prevented from making the application within such period. Section 285 (3) *Ibid*.

¹⁴⁶. Section 285 (2) *Ibid*.

¹⁴⁷. Section 285 (2) (a) and (b) *Ibid*.

¹⁴⁸. Section 286 (1) (a) and (b) *Ibid*.

¹⁴⁹. PIA.

assessment. The Service can only proceed to collect and recover hydrocarbon tax where the assessment is final and conclusive and the tax has not been paid.

7.0 Comparison with Other Jurisdictions

Taxation in the petroleum sector in Ghana is governed by the Petroleum Income Tax Act.¹⁵⁰ The basis for the imposition of tax in the jurisdiction in Ghana is found in the provision of Section 1 of the Act¹⁵¹, which provides that “a person conducting petroleum operations shall, subject to this Act, pay for each year of assessment a tax on chargeable income calculated in the manner provided in this Act.” Significantly, to be taxable under the Act, the person must be engaged in “petroleum operations” and by the provisions of Section 38 of the Act,¹⁵² what constitute “petroleum operations” has been defined to include exploration, development or production operations and operations for the sale, or export without sale of petroleum, which are operations carried out by a contractor.¹⁵³

The definition of “petroleum operations” in the jurisdiction in Ghana covers other sectors of the petroleum industry, unlike in Nigeria where it is restricted to activities in the upstream petroleum section. In Ghana the chargeable tax payable by a person conducting petroleum operations in respect of a year of assessment or quarterly period shall be 50% of the chargeable income arising from the operations in respect of that year or period, however, a person conducting petroleum operations may enter into an agreement to which may require that person to make alternative provision for the payment at a different rate, or at other rate otherwise payable under the section.¹⁵⁴ Another striking difference is that in Ghana the PITA is administered by the Commissioner,¹⁵⁵ who is responsible for the assessment and collection of the tax chargeable under this Act,¹⁵⁶ unlike in Nigeria where the Federal Inland Revenue Service and the Commission administered the Act.¹⁵⁷ Basically, there are no much

¹⁵⁰. 1987

¹⁵¹. PITA, 1987.

¹⁵². S. 38 (2) PITA, *ibid*.

¹⁵³. *Ibid*

¹⁵⁴. Section 6 PITA

¹⁵⁵ By Section 38 PITA. “Commissioner” means the Commissioner of the Internal Revenue Service

¹⁵⁶. Section 29 PITA

¹⁵⁷. Section 259 PIA, 2021.

differences between the practice in Ghana and what is obtainable in Nigeria in term of assessment to tax and filing of returns.

8.0 Findings

The following are the findings reached at the end of this research;

1. Hydrocarbon taxation is a major source of government revenue in Nigeria and to enhance the effective administration of hydrocarbon tax in the upstream petroleum sector, there is therefore need for a special attention to be given to the administration, collection and assessment of hydrocarbon tax.
2. The Act sets out to impose hydrocarbon tax on the profit of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations, however, the Act does not define what constitutes hydrocarbon, in view of the fact that hydrocarbon taxation is a major source of revenue to the Federal government of Nigeria, there is therefore need to delineate the scope of what constitute hydrocarbon.
3. The extant position of the law, according to the decision of the Supreme Court in Shell's case, with respect to the interpretation of the words "all outgoings and expenses wholly, exclusively and necessarily incurred for the purpose of petroleum operations" is that once there is statutory and contractual obligations for a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations to perform such statutory and contractual obligations it qualify as outgoings and expenses wholly, exclusively and necessarily incurred for the purpose of petroleum operations.

9.0 Recommendation

1. The provisions of the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021 should be amended in order to provide a clear definition of the word "hydrocarbon" and delineate the scope of what constitute hydrocarbon for the purpose of certainty and fairness of hydrocarbon tax system or regime.
2. There is need for the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021 to be amended to set the statutory limit of what amount to outgoings and expenses wholly, exclusively and necessarily incurred for the purpose of upstream petroleum operations.

3. The audited account of companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations be subjected to forensic examination by a body of external auditors appointed by the Nigeria Revenue Service to ascertain whether the returns made by the companies correspond with the actual profits of those companies in the accounting period in reference.

10.0 Conclusion

The administration and collection of Government revenue in the petroleum industry is vested on the Federal Inland Revenue Service¹⁵⁸ under the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021, however, with the repealed of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (Establishment) Act,¹⁵⁹ by the Nigeria Revenue Service (Establishment) Act¹⁶⁰, 2025, the administration and collection of taxes in Nigeria become the functions of the Nigeria Revenue Service.¹⁶¹ The Nigeria Tax Act, 2025,¹⁶² in Chapter 3, reenacted the provisions of Chapter 4 of the Petroleum Industry, 2021 and part two of the said chapter reintroduced Petroleum Profits Tax which was earlier repealed by the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021. Similarly, the provisions of part 1-X of chapter four of the Petroleum Industry Act,¹⁶³ have been amended by the Nigeria Tax Act¹⁶⁴, 2025.

Though, the Nigeria Tax Act, 2025, amended the provisions of part 1-X of chapter four of the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021, the amendments are merely to the effect that the provisions of chapter four of the Petroleum Industry Act, are now contained in the Nigeria Tax, Act, 2025. Therefore, the tenor of the tax regime under the Petroleum Industry Act remains the same with the regime under the Nigeria Tax Act, with somewhat different of reintroduction of petroleum profits tax under the Nigeria Tax Act, 2025.

This work demonstrated that the proper taxation of hydrocarbon tax begins with the determination of the assessable and chargeable tax without which there cannot be an

¹⁵⁸. S. 259 PIA, 2021.

¹⁵⁹. No. 13 2007

¹⁶⁰. This Act came as a result of the Tax Reform policy of the President Bola Ahmed Tinubu.

¹⁶¹. S. 4 Nigeria Revenue Service (Establishment) Act, 2025.

¹⁶². Which is one of the legislations recently passed into law in furtherance of the Tax Reform Policy of President Tinubu.

¹⁶³. PIA, 2021

¹⁶⁴. S. 198 (1) Nigeria Tax Act, 2025.

accurate assessment of the hydrocarbon tax of a company engaged in upstream petroleum operations. It also elucidated the conceptual basis for taxation of hydrocarbon tax, ascertainment of chargeable profits, adjusted profits, and assessable profits, chargeable profits as well as assessable and chargeable tax and assessment of hydrocarbon tax and made findings and recommendations.